

pH-metric studies of copper(II) and thorium(IV) complexes with substituted pyrazolines and pyrazoles

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Complex formation of Cu^{II} and Th^{IV} with 3-(4-methyl-7-hydroxycoumaryl)-5-aryl-1H-pyrazole and 3-(4-methyl-7-hydroxycoumaryl)-4-(4'-methoxybenzoyl)-5-(4''-methoxyphenyl)-1-carboxamidopyrazoline have been studied at $27 \pm 1^\circ$ and 0.1 M ionic strength in 70% DMF-water mixture. The stability constants of the complexes indicate simultaneous formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal-ligand complexes in both the cases.

Pyrazoles and pyrazolines act as good complexing agents. Metal-ligand stability constant of lanthanides have been studied with some substituted pyrazolines and diketones¹. The interaction of Co^{II} , Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} with certain substituted pyrazoles have also been studied².

Hence, it is of interest to study the stability constants of Cu^{II} and Th^{IV} complexes with 3-(4-methyl-7-hydroxycoumaryl)-5-aryl-1H-pyrazole (L^{1H}) and 3-(4-methyl-7-hydroxycoumaryl)-4-(4'-methoxybenzoyl)-5-(4''-methoxyphenyl)-1-carboxamidopyrazoline (L^{2H}). The present equilibrium study has been carried out at $27 \pm 1^\circ$ and at a constant ionic strength, $I = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (NaClO_4).

Results and discussion

The ligands L^{1H} and L^{2H} function as monoprotic acids due to deprotonation of the phenolic OH group.

(L^{1H})

(L^{2H})

The successive stability constant values (Table 1) for both the Cu^{II} and Th^{IV} complexes are found to be quite close. This indicates simultaneous complex formation. It could be seen from Table 1 that $\text{p}K$ value of L^{2H} is slightly higher than that of L^{1H} because of the electron-releasing effect of two methoxyphenyl groups in the forms. Stability constants of the Cu^{II} and Th^{IV} complexes with pyrazoline are higher as compared to those with pyrazole. This may be due to the electron-releasing effect of two methoxyphenyl groups. In L^{2} -metal complexes, CONH_2 group acts as a base and generally basicity of ligand increases stability of the complexes. There is possibility of formation of complex in solid state and not in solution due to insolubility of ligand in solvent (aq.), so there is no scope for additional coordination with the amide group.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of AnalaR grade. Ligands L^{1H}

Table 1. Proton-ligand and metal-ligand constants with DMF-water mixture : 70%, temp. = $27 \pm 1^\circ$, $I = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (NaClO_4)

Ligand	$\text{p}K^{\text{H}}$	Cu^{II}		Th^{IV}	
		$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$
L^{1H}	7.20 ± 0.03	6.19 ± 0.055	5.39 ± 0.045	6.59 ± 0.060	5.70 ± 0.050
L^{2H}	7.72 ± 0.035	7.09 ± 0.045	6.31 ± 0.070	6.89 ± 0.055	6.28 ± 0.045

and L^2H were prepared according to literature method³. Both the ligands were crystallized and their purity was checked by TLC before use. The solutions of ligands were prepared in DMF and standardized according to literature method⁴.

A Systronics pH-meter (μ -pH-Sys-362) with glass electrode and saturated calomel electrode was used.

The experimental procedure involved potentiometric titrations of (i) free ($HClO_4$) acid (0.01 M), (ii) free ($HClO_4$) acid (0.01 M) and ligand (20×10^{-4} M) and (iii) free ($HClO_4$) acid (0.01 M) and ligand (20×10^{-4} M) + metal (4×10^{-4} M) against standard (0.1 M) NaOH solution. The initial volume of each solution was taken as 50 ml. The ionic strength of all the solutions was maintained constant (0.1 M) by adding an appropriate quantity of 1 M sodium perchlorate.

The titrations were carried out in 100-ml pyrex glass

beaker kept in a water-bath maintained at constant temperature (27 ± 0.1). Nitrogen gas was purged for maintaining inert atmosphere. Deprotonation constants (pK^H) of the ligand and stability constants ($\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$) were calculated by following the method of Irving and Rossotti⁵.

References

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